

Studies in Formation and Properties of Carbon-Oxygen Surface Complexes. Part III. Effect of the Complexes on Sorption of Water and Benzene Vapours by Charcoals and Carbon blacks

Balwant Rai Puri and S. K. Sharma

A study of water and benzene sorption isotherms on various samples of charcoal and carbon black coated with different types of carbon-oxygen surface complexes shows that the presence of acidic CO₂-complex imparts a polar and hydrophilic character to the carbon surface whereby adsorption of water is enhanced at all relative vapour pressures. The complex appears to provide sites where additional water is sorbed through a mechanism probably involving hydrogen bonding. The non-acidic CO₂-complex and the CO-complex are not involved much in influencing the water isotherms. The CO-complex, however, improves adsorbability of benzene vapours which is probably due to interaction of π electrons of benzene with quinone groups present as a part of CO-complex.

The presence of combined oxygen is known to enhance the sorption of water vapour, particularly at lower relative vapour pressures, on charcoals and carbon blacks, to an appreciable extent¹⁻⁵. According to Pierce³ *et al.*, the increase is due to an extensive reaction of water with the surface oxygen complexes. Pierce and Smith⁴ and McDermot and Arnell⁵ attribute the increase to the formation of 'clumps' or 'clusters' of water molecules at the active sites provided by the combined oxygen through a mechanism involving hydrogen bonding. According to Puri⁶ *et al.* these active sites are provided by the oxygen evolved as carbon dioxide (CO₂-complex). In view of the fact, however, that CO₂-complex itself is of two types, one acidic and the other non-acidic, as has been shown recently⁷, and the CO-complex also includes some polar oxygen in the form of phenolic and quinonic groups⁸, it was thought of interest to investigate the influence of various oxygen complexes on the sorption of water and benzene vapours on carbons in some details. The present work was, therefore, undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Charcoal prepared by the carbonisation of cane sugar⁹ and a few samples of commercial carbon blacks were used in the present investigations. Sugar charcoal and one of the carbon blacks (Mogul) were also outgassed at increasing temperatures upto 1000° in the manner explained before⁹. Sugar charcoal, was also treated with aqueous hydrogen peroxide and

1. R. B. Anderson and P. H. Emmett, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1947, **51**, 1308.
2. M. M. Dubinin, E. D. Zaverina and V. V. Serpinski, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1760.
3. C. Pierce, R. N. Smith, J. W. Wiley and H. Cordes, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4551.
4. C. Pierce and R. N. Smith, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1950, **54**, 784.
5. H. L. McDermot and J. C. Arnell, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 492.
6. B. R. Puri, K. Murari and D. D. Singh, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 37.
7. B. R. Puri, G. K. Sharma and S. K. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 64.
8. B. R. Puri and K. M. Bedi, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 215.
9. B. R. Puri, N. K. Sandle and O. P. Mahajan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4880.

acidified potassium persulphate resulting in further chemisorption of oxygen mostly as acidic CO_2 -complex⁷. The same charcoal, outgassed at 1000° , was treated with acidified potassium persulphate and potassium permanganate resulting in chemisorption of oxygen mostly as non-acidic CO_2 -complex and as CO -complex⁷.

The oxygen content and its disposition as carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide and water vapour was obtained in each case on evacuation, in a resistance tube furnace at 1000° .⁹ Base adsorption capacity was obtained, as before⁷, by mixing charcoal or carbon black (1 g.) with 0.2 *N* barium hydroxide (100 ml.), shaking the suspension for about 48 hr and titrating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid against a standard acid. These values, in most cases, were equivalent to the amount of carbon dioxide evolved when expressed in similar units, as shown in Table I. The difference wherever in excess of 2% was taken as the amount of non-acidic CO_2 -complex, as before⁷. The results of various determinations are given in Table I. The B.E.T. nitrogen surface areas are also included.

Adsorption isotherms were determined at 35° by using McBain's quartz spring balance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The adsorption isotherms of water on various samples of sugar charcoal are plotted in Fig. 1. It may be noted, in the first instance, that outgassing at increasing temperatures

Fig. 1. Water vapour adsorption isotherms on sugar charcoal before and after various treatments.

upto 700° (cf. curves 1, 2 and 3) results in lowering the capacity of charcoal to adsorb water vapour at all relative vapour pressures. There is no further significant change in the shape or content of the isotherm on outgassing the charcoal at 1000° (cf. curve 4). Since the isotherms on 700° - and 1000° -outgassed charcoals do not differ materially from each other and since 700° is the temperature at which the entire amount of the acidic CO_2 -complex is eliminated, although more than 3% of the oxygen, present as CO -complex, is still retained

(Table I), it appears that the CO_2 -complex affects moisture sorption capacity of charcoal to a far larger extent than the CO -complex. The isotherms on Mogul before and after outgassing at 700° and 1000° (Fig. 2) also show similar trends. The above view was further checked by determining water isotherms on the original sugar charcoal after extending its acidic CO_2 -complex, on treatment with aqueous hydrogen peroxide as well as acidified potassium persulphate (cf. Table I). It is seen that the isotherms (Fig. 1, curves 5 and 6) shift bodily upward to an appreciable extent, the moisture sorption increasing almost in proportion to increase in the acidic CO_2 -complex.

Fig. 2. Water vapour adsorption isotherms on Mogul before and after outgassing at 700° and 1000° .

All the isotherms show inflection at about 0.4 or 0.5 relative vapour pressure after which there is a more rapid rise in the sorption value in each case. This indicates occurrence of capillary condensation at higher relative vapour pressures.

In order to understand the extent to which the presence of acidic CO_2 -complex enhances water sorption at a given relative vapour pressure, the amounts of water sorbed in excess of that taken up by 700° -outgassed charcoal (which was entirely free of CO_2 -complex) was plotted against the corresponding amount of the complex present in the various samples of sugar charcoal. The plots of the values obtained at 0.2 and 0.5 relative vapour pressures, upto which the results are not likely to be vitiated by the occurrence of capillary condensation, are shown in Fig. 3. It is seen that the points fit well around a straight line at each relative vapour pressure. The slope of the line for 0.20 r.v.p. indicates that roughly one mole of additional water is taken up for one mole of acidic CO_2 -complex while that of the line at 0.50 r.v.p. indicates sorption of water close to two moles of additional water per mole of the complex. These observations appear to be in accord with the view of certain workers⁴⁷⁵ that additional water, in the presence of combined oxygen, is adsorbed at the oxygen sites in the form of clusters through a mechanism involving hydrogen bonding and that these clusters grow in size as more and more water is adsorbed at increasing vapour pressures.

However, there is one important difference. The sites for the sorption of water through the mechanism of hydrogen bonding are provided by the oxygen present as acidic CO_2 -complex and not by the total combined oxygen, as suggested by the above workers.

Fig. 3. Increase in the sorption of water vapour at 0.2 and 0.5 r.v.p. with increase in the amount of the acidic CO_2 -complex.

Water isotherms on a few carbon blacks described in Table I were also determined. Since these samples differed appreciably in their surface areas, in order to get comparable

Fig. 4. Water vapour adsorbed by carbon blacks at different relative vapour pressures in relation to total oxygen content.

values, it was necessary to calculate the amount of water sorbed per unit surface at a given relative vapour pressure and to plot it against the oxygen content per unit surface. The plots of sorption values per unit surface upto 0.5 r.v.p. against total oxygen content per unit surface are shown in Fig. 4 and against acidic oxygen per unit surface in Fig. 5. It is

Fig. 5. Water vapour adsorbed by carbon blacks at different relative vapour pressures in relation to acidic CO_2 -complex.

seen that although there is increase in moisture sorption at all r.v.p.s with increase in oxygen content, the points fit around a straight line only when the sorption values are plotted against the acidic CO_2 -complex (Fig. 5). These observations support the view that the acidic oxygen is involved much more than the rest of the combined oxygen in enhancing sorption of water vapour.

The effect of non-acidic CO_2 -complex which has been shown⁷ to come into existence on treatment of outgassed charcoals with oxygen at elevated temperatures or with oxidising solutions at ordinary temperatures was studied by determining isotherms on 1000° -outgassed charcoal after treatment with acidified potassium persulphate and permanganate. These treatments, as shown in Table I, cause an appreciable chemisorption of oxygen as CO_2 -complex which is mostly non-acidic. The sorption values on these samples at different relative vapour pressures, plotted in Fig. 1, are not much different from the corresponding values on 1000° -outgassed charcoal which was essentially free from oxygen. Thus fixation of oxygen as non-acidic CO_2 -complex, like that of oxygen present as CO -complex does not appear to have any noticeable influence on the sorption of water vapour by charcoal.

Since the acidic CO_2 -complex renders carbon surface polar and improves adsorbability of polar vapours, it may have adverse effect on adsorbability of non-polar vapours. It was thought of interest, therefore, to study adsorption isotherms of benzene on the original as well as outgassed samples of sugar charcoal and Mogul. It is seen (Figs. 6 and 7) that the

Fig. 6. Benzene vapour adsorption isotherms on Mogul before and after outgassing at 700° and 1000° .

presence of the acidic complex in the original charcoal or the carbon black affects adversely the sorption of benzene vapour, as expected. The elimination of this complex on outgassing

Fig. 7. Benzene vapour adsorption isotherms on 1000° -outgassed sugar charcoal before and after various treatments.

at 700° renders the surface much more benzophilic as there is a considerable increase in the sorption values at all relative vapour pressures. There is another point of special interest. The samples outgassed at 700°, in spite of their oxygen, show greater sorption of benzene than those outgassed at 1000°, which are free of combined oxygen, do. This anomaly appears to be due to interaction of quinone groups which form a part of CO-complex⁸ with π -electrons of benzene. Possibilities of such interactions in organic chemistry have been suggested¹⁰.

The influence of CO-complex in enhancing sorption of benzene vapour was checked further by determining benzene isotherms on 1000°-outgassed charcoal after building a small concentration of CO-complex on its surface on treatment with acidified potassium permanganate, as shown in Table I. It is seen (curve 4, Fig. 7) that the formation of even a small amount of the CO-complex causes an appreciable increase in the sorption of benzene at all relative vapour pressures.

Several workers^{11,12,13} have been trying to correlate polarities of carbon surface with total combined oxygen without caring to split the latter into different types of surface complexes or surface oxide groups, assuming tacitly that the combined oxygen has, more or less, a uniform effect. This view cannot be correct in the light of the observations recorded above. It appears that while a part of the combined oxygen, which comes off as carbon dioxide, and imparts acidity, also imparts polarity to carbon surface; another part, also coming off as carbon dioxide, is almost ineffective, and still another part, that comes off as carbon monoxide, imparts benzophilic character to carbon surface.

Department of Chemistry,
Panjab University,
Chandigarh.

Received February 8, 1970

10. N. S. Bhacca, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, **41**, 3127.
11. R. B. Anderson and P. H. Emmett, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 753.
12. G. Krause, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 343.
13. J. J. Kipling and D. B. Peakaal, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 834.

